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Teaching Gen Z Learners: Challenges and Coping Strategies

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Teaching has always been a challenging profession, but with the rise of Generation Z (Gen Z) learners, educators are facing a whole new set of challenges. Gen Z learners, also known as the iGeneration, are those students born between the mid-1990s through the late 2010s (Moscrip, 2019). They are the first generation to have grown up entirely in the digital age, and this has had a significant impact on their learning styles and behaviors. As educators, it is crucial to understand these challenges and adapt our teaching methods to ensure the success of our Gen Z learners.

One of the main challenges in teaching Gen Z learners is their short attention span which can last for 8 seconds only (Azmy, Hosen, Hassan, Ismail, Abdul Rahim, & Tarmidi, 2022; Hampton & Keys, 2016). As they grow in a digital world, Gen Z learners have been exposed to distractions and technology addiction (Yalçın-İncik & İncik, 2022). This has made it difficult for them to focus on one task for an extended period. As a result, educators need to find creative ways to keep their students engaged and interested in the subject matter. This may involve incorporating technology into the classroom which can arouse their interest (Udto & Kusain, 2023). Further, using interactive activities and incorporating real-life examples can make the lessons more relatable to them (Lopez & Abadiano, 2023).

Another challenge is the need for instant gratification. Gen Z learners are highly dependent on technology (Saracho, 2023) and have grown up in a world where everything is available at the click of a button. They are used to getting immediate responses and results, and this can lead to impatience in learning. As educators, we need to be mindful of this and find ways to make the learning process more engaging and rewarding for them. This could involve setting achievable goals and providing instant feedback to keep them motivated.

Moreover, Gen Z learners have a different approach to learning compared to previous generations. They are digital natives, meaning they are comfortable using technology in all aspects of their lives. As mentioned by Lopez and Abadiano (2023), technology is their identity. This has resulted in a preference for visual and interactive learning over traditional methods such as lectures and textbooks. Hence,

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to effectively teach Gen Z learners, educators must embrace technology and incorporate it into their teaching methods. This could include using educational apps, videos, and online resources to supplement traditional teaching methods.

Finally, Gen Z learners are exposed to different cultures, beliefs, and opinions as they communicate indefinitely across the globe (Jima'ain, Wan Ibrisaam Fik, Alias, & Mohamad, n.d.) and this has shaped their perspective about the world. As educators, it is crucial to create a safe and inclusive learning environment that celebrates diversity and encourages open-mindedness. This can be achieved by incorporating diverse perspectives and experiences into the curriculum and promoting respectful discussions and debates among students.

To conclude, teaching Gen Z learners comes with its unique set of challenges. However, by understanding their learning styles and adapting our teaching methods, we can effectively engage and educate this generation. As educators, it is our responsibility to keep up with the changing times and ensure that our teaching methods are relevant and effective in preparing Gen Z learners for the future.

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